

Transcription of Interview 4

*for Shane Murphy
November 2020*

Shane: ..there's only four overarching questions, that, largely, just look to explore your views and opinions on the National Health Insurance.

Interviewee 4: Okay, yes, I definitely don't have an hour, the max I can do, is half an hour.

Shane: That's more than enough.

Interviewee 4: Okay, great stuff.

Shane: Okay. So my first question, rather broadly, is, what is your view on the National Health Insurance?

Interviewee 4: Well, I've sort of got mixed feelings about it. It depends on the actual way it's being implemented. I think it could be a good thing, if the methodology is good, and the process is well-planned, and all aspects is considered; so in that sense, I think it can work. We'll just have to see how government plans it. That's what my feelings are, at this point in time.

Shane: Okay. Why do you have hesitancy, around the possibility of it working?

Interviewee 4: Well, I am working for government, so I know that things have to be carefully planned, and efficiency needs to play the role with these many stakeholders, systems, so which would be your.. if you look at, well, systems, yes, all the recording, reporting, logistical systems, and then the human resource systems, to make it happen; and their level of accountability and governance. So all those aspects contribute to the success factor of such a system. So that is why I have some.. little bit not sure whether it would work or not work. And I just think it's a very big undertaking, but I guess if it's carefully planned, it will be fine.

Shane: Okay. And your view of the funding of the NHI? How do you think it will, or should be funded?

Interviewee 4: Well, what I understand of it, is that, I guess, there will be a sort of, in terms of individuals contributing, there should be sort of a sliding scale, and I'm assuming that the higher your income bracket, the more you will contribute, and the lower, the lesser. And I guess, *it's something*, almost similar to access to water in a city, that if you are earning.. well, everybody gets five litres free water, but, so it will be like a sliding scale, what your contribution is. So the lesser your income, and if you've got no income, obviously, there's nothing you can contribute; but everybody will contribute proportionate to their income.

And then, obviously, from the bigger hospitals, the existing private sector, I'm assuming that those resources will be brought in, and the access to the better service, or the better structural systems, and possibly other facilities, that will become available. So I'm not sure how it's going to work with the existing bigger infrastructure that we have in the private sector, private hospitals, and so on, but ja, that

is how I assume. So you won't have a medical aid, but you have a choice if you want to top-up. I think if you've got a medical aid, you've got to top-up because it's not enough. So ja, that's how I think it should all be working; I'm not sure if I'm right, but that's what I think.

Shane: Yes. And the idea behind separating the purchaser from the funder, the so-called, strategic purchasing, do you think that's a good idea?

Interviewee 4: Ah, ja, that's where the other challenges can come in. Obviously, if the strategic purchasing or funding depends on which way that it's going to be done, if it's on a tender route, similar to the medications that we get now, so again, I think that would work; when you do any specification of any **core..** or documentations, such as tender documents, or large documents for funding purposes, it's all dependent on the person that actually writes the document, and the knowledge of that person, and the thinking outside of the box, type of thing, also your negotiation ability, ability to negotiate the best deal, to get the best benefit for the money that you have available to purchase the service that you're going to purchase.

[05:57]

So ja, it's all dependant on that. I know that with my work life; I've got to write tenders, but I'm not that bright to understand tenders; you have to have the qualifications, and things like that. So that limits; and you see other examples, like cellphone contracts we have, the guys didn't do proper negotiations, or good negotiations. Sometimes the deal is not as good as you wanted it to be, and then you only realise, looking back, that, oh dear, there's my mistakes; but then it's too late, you're stuck in it for three years, or something like that. But that means that it shouldn't be done by a small team, it should be done by a broader multisectoral team, with financial capabilities and skills, and specialists, in terms of what is required. So ja, that's my thoughts.

Shane: In your experience, would you say that the NHI has followed that multidisciplinary team, in developing the proposal and the rollout?

Interviewee 4: I'm not sure, I've not really looked at it from that perspective. No, I haven't really.. I know about.. I know the content and so forth, but I'm not following it in such great deal, I can't say; no, I don't know.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to your own personal engagement in the policy development, have you ever had any discussions or requests for input?

Interviewee 4: No, nothing into the policy. The only thing that we, indirectly, have, is the core norms and standards, and the ideal clinic implementation, and ensuring that all facilities met the requirements of the core norms and standards; and indirectly, hearing about the inspections that's been done. It doesn't directly affect me. So ja, that's how I've been engaged. But no, I'm not at that level that anybody would ever want, I think, my input into it.

Shane: And what do you think it would be like, to engage with the private sector? Do you think that they're willing, or see it as a threat?

Interviewee 4: I think it's going to be positive. They see it as a threat, at this point in time. But I think it depends; a small minority is really running the – if I could say – the private sector now, and lately, now, with the GP Care Cell that we're busy rolling out, and the [...] programme, I'm actually surprised at the eagerness of some of the medical professionals, to participate.

So I'm thinking that those that are running these private sector institutions, are probably quite a small minority, and I think that private practices, on its own, is having a hard time competing with places like Medcross, and **where** a larger team can offer a better offering to their patients. And hence, I think, it's probably going to be better equitable share for private sector, and I think it's going to be positive; it will also make everything more accessible to the community at large. And ja, as long as it doesn't become expensive to get the service, if you've got a better income than others, it should still be affordable for you.

[10:25]

Shane: Yes. And Mr Interviewee 4, the state of the current public service, do you think that it's ready to implement NHI?

Interviewee 4: Well look, I can only talk from primary healthcare perspective. We have really tried, our budget was not always there, our Executive Director that's just left us, we all wanted the platinum, and there has been reporting back on progress, we had to purchase a lot of items to meet the minimum requirements, and I think our facilities are coming onboard. You can see that the overall.. how the facilities look, and what is available, and I think the standard is definitely increasing; and I think we're going there, we're definitely not there, we're struggling. And also, what happens is, we fall back; you will score 85, this time, at the evaluation, and then next time.. it's difficult to maintain systems, and then the next call, well, you fall back. So the proof is really in meeting, at every evaluation, the similar, or even better scores, than what you had previously.

And I think facility managers are now knowing what's expected of them, and what must be done. There's still a lot to be done; I mean, if we do clinical record audit, there's still a lot of big gaps, that is probably our worst performing, is recording reporting; and I think, often, that is related to the high volumes of what is being seen by the facilities. But we're going there, we're trying, as primary healthcare service [...] for Med school perspective; we're trying to put the resources.. and every year, when the review of the budget, or there's **more** funding, what our needs are, or what we weren't able to provide last year, for instance, like the generators, uninterrupted electricity supply, that is one of the things, that we worked on, that a good example of that, is when we talked, earlier, about things going wrong; you're always dependant on your quotations, like we're putting call-out for generators.

So if your **proposal** document wasn't good, and you still have to take the cheapest tender, that is where the problems go wrong. So we do have the generators now, but we do have lots of unforeseen problems, to ensure that there's still uninterrupted electrical supply at the clinics.

But I think, over time, one's learning to see what's your mistake with that tender, that documentation. So ja, we're getting there, slowly but surely. But we are set to do that, to meet the requirements of the core norms and standards, and ideal clinic. So ja, everybody's working positive towards that.

Shane: And going forward, what do you think would be the major challenges, and the post-solutions, to implementing NHI?

Interviewee 4: I think, now, I hear the hearings is on; I wasn't part of the recent hearings that took place, people could be part, and hear. So I think it's to listen to the community, and hear what all the stakeholders has to say, and to see how one can accommodate, because if one considers the broader view by stakeholders, and see how we can tweak the system, that it will be a win/win situation for all stakeholders, and all of the community at large, from the uninsured population to the insured population; that's, I think, one of the things. So it's to review what was the thoughts, and to listen to recommendations, and then changing what was original plan, to what could be better solutions.

[15:40]

And then, secondly, I guess, I'm not sure how to make it happen; maybe a phased approach, we start at primary healthcare level. I don't know, I really don't have a idea what's the way. But I think that's the biggest thing, that I would think, would be important. But for us, and the other hurdle would be the sustainability of issues, like I've mentioned to you earlier, our facilities would score a 85 or the platinum, and then they fall back, straight down to a silver, at the next stage; because you've got staff that change over. And also you need to have dedication to maintain the systems, and not work just for the sake of the evaluation, and then we go on with life, and then when it's evaluation time, quickly run around and fix. So it should be a sustainable plan, that can be easily maintained by the providers of the services, and integrity, ensuring that it needs the minimum that is required, at all times. So ja, that's, basically, what I think.

Shane: Okay.

Interviewee 4: I'm not very knowledgeable in this subject, you've got the wrong person.

Shane: No, you're adding so much value. I'd just like to know, you speak a lot to the monitoring and evaluation, and the response; and do you think that that system, currently, is fully functional and adequate, for the implementation of the NHI? Or what would you change about it?

Interviewee 4: I think it's adequate; I believe it's been given a timeframe, and that this year is our last year of, I think, it's quarterly reviews. I think that is wrong; it should be, probably, if now maybe quarterly reviews is a bit over the top; but I would think, at least, biannual, would be good. And I think the system, as they planned, with the inspectors, the unexpected drop-in visit by inspectors, that is good; because it's always good to get an external view, but it's also there to know it's keeping you on your toes. And possibly.. I don't know if they're going to couple it with, where, if you don't meet the requirements, you will be given a fine; so that, you're not meeting.. And also for them to go back, and to say, the fine should not be something light, it should be heavy, so that people ensure that it happens.

And obviously, this is just about the accessibility, it also needs to be applicable to the quality of the service, that reviews of clinical audits, and service customer care surveys, all those should be done to ensure that the system meets the requirements that is there. And then, obviously, it must not be so rigid that it cannot change, because we don't know how it's going to work. So one see if it works, it works; if

it doesn't work, what can we do better. So put systems in place, to say, okay, that's going to be a review. And then, obviously, there's going to be timeframes for awarding or for who gets what, so that there's an equitable share amongst all stakeholders, in terms of, I'm talking about the service delivering offering.

[20:10]

Shane: Okay. So then, that's all of the questions from my side. Is there any other comment or view, that you would like to express?

Interviewee 4: No, I think that's what I can contribute, at the current moment, and I don't have additional views, no.

Shane: As soon as I get the interview transcribed onto MS Word, I'll send you a copy, so that you could review it and change anything, if you would like. But thanks so much.

Interviewee 4: I don't think I will change anything; don't you worry, I'm too busy to worry about that. I've done what I can, within the time that I have. So it's fine, you may do that, but I don't think I'm going to feel bad about something that I said; definitely not.

Shane: Okay, perfect. And thanks so much for taking the time, I really appreciate it, and it's added a lot of value.

Interviewee 4: Okay, no problem, thank you.

Shane: Alright, have a good day.

Interviewee 4: Bye.

-----oOo-----